

A New *bla_{VIM}* Gene in a *Pseudomonas putida* Isolated from ENT Units in Sulaimani Hospitals

Dalanya Asaad Mohammed, and Dara Abdul Razaq

Abstract—A total of twenty tonsillectomy biopsies were collected from children undergoing tonsillectomy from teaching hospital ENT department and Kurdistan private hospital in Sulaimani city. All biopsies were homogenized and cultured; the obtained bacterial isolates were purified and identified by biochemical tests and VITEK 2 compact system. Among the twenty studied samples, only one *Pseudomonas putida* with probability of 99% was isolated. Antimicrobial susceptibility was carried out by disk diffusion method, *Pseudomonas putida* showed resistance to all antibiotics used except vancomycin. The isolate further subjected to PCR and DNA sequence analysis of *bla_{VIM}* gene using different set of primers for different regions of *VIM* gene. The results were found to be PCR positive for the *bla_{VIM}* gene. To determine the sequence of *bla_{VIM}* gene, DNA sequencing performed. Sequence alignment of *bla_{VIM}* gene with previously recorded *bla_{VIM}* gene in NCBI- database showed that *P. putida* isolate have different *bla_{VIM}* gene.

Keywords—Clinical isolates, Putida, Sulaimani, Vim gene.

I. INTRODUCTION

MICROORGANISMS might exhibit resistance to drugs by many different mechanisms. The most important mechanism is β -lactamase enzymes production, which are a group of enzymes capable of hydrolysing the 4-membered β -lactam ring of beta-lactam antibiotics [1], which can be either chromosomally encoded or plasmid mediated [11]. Several novel MBLs were identified, including VIM-1 from *P. aeruginosa* and IMP-2 from *Acinetobacter baumannii* in Italy [15], VIM-2 from *P. putida* in France [119], and IMP-3 from *Shigella flexneri* in Japan. The spread of MBLs in gram-negative rods has been described in several other countries and is becoming an emerging threat [7]. It remains unknown whether these MBLs have appeared in other countries. The aim of the study is to identify the molecular mechanism of the multidrug resistant *P. putida* among the isolates.

II. METHODS

A. Isolation and Identification

Samples were collected from Teaching Hospital (ENT Dept.) and Kurdistan Private Hospital. Biopsies were taken after tonsillectomy. Biopsy was transferred to laboratory in a sterile container which contains normal saline. Samples were

prepared for bacteriological examination by homogenization and centrifugation. Prepared samples were cultured on nutrient agar, and then single colonies were selected and inoculated on selective media for the purpose of obtaining pure cultures. Isolate identification performed microscopically, biochemical tests, and then the identification confirmed using VITEK 2 compact system.

B. Antimicrobial susceptibility and Isoelectric focusing of β -lactamase: Antibiotic-containing discs (BBL, Cockeysville, MD, USA) were used for routine antibiograms by disc diffusion assay. MICs of antimicrobial agents were determined by the agar dilution method. *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 were used as MIC reference strain. Modified Hodge and EDTA-disc synergy tests were performed for the screening of metallo- β -lactamase-producing strains. The results were compared to CLSI standard 2008. The isoelectric points of β -lactamases were determined by loading cell sonicates to precast pH 3 to 10 gels. The gel was overlaid with a filter paper soaked in 20 mM EDTA for 5 min, before the imipenem (0.5 mg/L)-containing Mueller–Hinton agar was added. In this manner, inhibition of imipenem-hydrolysing activities could be observed.

C. Molecular methods

Amplification of *VIM* gene of *pseudomonas putida* by direct colony PCR: A single bacterial colony which is previously cultured on nutrient agar was dissolved in 50 μ l dd H₂O (MQ). The cells suspension was incubated at 37°C water bath for at least 3 min. The cells were disrupted by heating by the insertion of the PCR tube containing the bacterial suspension into the thermocycler using the following program: 2 cycles for 10 min. at 99°C heating and 1 cycle for 5 min. at 4°C cooling. The samples were centrifuged at 13000 rpm for 10 minutes. The pellet was discarded and 5 μ l of supernatant were used as template in the PCR reactions. Master mix was prepared by adding 5 μ l of tag buffer, 2.5 μ l of (f and r) primer, 1 μ l of dNTP(10mM), 5 μ l of supernatant, 3 μ l MgCl₂, and 0.3 μ l tag polymerase to 30.7 μ l DDH₂O (50 μ l total volume in a sterile 0.5 ml PCR tube on ice). The PCR reactions were inserted into the PCR programs: A- PCR for the detection of VIM-type metallo-lactamase genes was carried out with primers VIM-DIA/f and VIM-DIA/r in a 50 μ l volume Reaction parameters were as follows: Annealing at 55°C for 60s extension at 72°C for 90s denaturation at 94°C for 50s for 25 cycles. The samples were analyzed by gel electrophoresis at 80V for 1 hr. The gel running was stopped and the DNA was visualized, and the DNA bands were

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photographed digitally. as was the preparation of recombinant plasmids containing PCR product, and transformation of them into *E. coli* DH5, Plasmids from successful clones were used to determine the sequence of the *bla_{VIM}* gene by the dideoxynucleotide-chain termination method, with an automatic DNA sequencer (ABI 3700, in Adden institute for molecular biology techniques/ Tehran- Iran The determination of the sequence was repeated with more than two clones from independent amplicons. Both strands were sequenced. Sequence alignment of *VIM* gene: Homology searches were conducted between the sequence of other reported sequences of *VIM* gene for *P. Putida* and other Gram negative bacteria in database of NCBI using BLAST program which is available at the NCBI online at (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov) and the sequence of the same gene of the natural isolates.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results showed that out of 20 samples, only one was positive for *Pseudomonas putida*, the identification levels (Confidence and probability) by VITEK 2 compact system was 99%. *Pseudomonas putida*, being that the bacterium rarely colonizes mucosal surfaces but from other previously reported cases, it was determined that risk factors for developing such infections include the insertion of catheters, intubation, and/or intravascular devices [3]. *P. putida* infection was found in contaminated bottle of StaKleer. StaKleer is an anti-fog solution used on mirrors and endoscopes to prevent condensation from occurring, allowing for the proper visualization of ear and nose tissues. Sometimes unopened bottles of the solution at the clinic were found to be contaminated with *Pseudomonas putida* [9]. Disc diffusion testing revealed that *Pseudomonas putida* local isolate was resistant to most β -lactams, including ampicillin, ampicillin-sulbactam, piperacillin, piperacillin-tazobactam, cefalothin, ceftazidime, ceftazidime and aztreonam. The isolate was also resistant to tobramycin, intermediate to gentamicin, but susceptible to amikacin and ciprofloxacin. MICs of imipenem and meropenem for the isolate were 4 mg/L, and that of aztreonam was 64 mg/L. MICs of ampicillin, ampicillin-sulbactam, piperacillin, piperacillin-tazobactam, cefalothin, ceftazidime, ceftazidime and ceftazidime were >128 mg/L. Isoelectric focusing of extract of the isolate showed two β -lactamase bands of pI ~5.3 and 9.0. The isolate showed positive modified Hodge and EDTA-disc synergy tests, and the only pI 5.3 band was no longer present when the gels were overlaid with EDTA, which are findings suggesting a metallo- β -lactamase. The band of pI ~9.0 was likely to be chromosomal AmpC cephalosporinase. A plasmid harbouring a carbapenem resistance determinant was not detected (data not shown). These results suggest that a metallo- β -lactamase gene may be located on the chromosome. VIM-2 metallo- β -lactamase has no hydrolytic activity against aztreonam, but the MIC of aztreonam for *P.putida* was 64 mg/L, which is higher than the resistant breakpoint. This result was possibly due to production of a chromosomal cephalosporinase (pI ~9.0). The gel electrophoresis analysis showed a band about 800 bp for *bla_{VIM}* gene in accordance with *bla_{VIM}* gene sequence. Carbapenem-hydrolyzing metallo- β -lactamases, especially

IMP-type and VIM-type metallo- β -lactamases, are clinically important, because these enzymes effectively hydrolyze almost all β -lactam antibiotics except monobactams, conferring resistance to penicillins and cefepime in addition to carbapenems on pathogenic bacteria. Since genes encoding these metallo- β -lactamases (*bla_{IMP}* and *bla_{VIM}*) and their variant genes have become easy to detect using the PCR method, since 1989 the dissemination of these genes in clinical isolates has been widely observed in gram-negative bacteria, especially in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and other non-glucose-fermenting bacteria [16]. Multiple-drug resistance *P. putida* isolates producing VIM-type metallo- β -lactamases were reported in Italy as a causative species of nosocomial infections. [14, 19, 4, 8]. Luzzaro *et al.*, 2004 [7] reported that the sizes of the integron carrying the *bla_{VIM}* varied among the isolates from 3 to 6 kb. Prevalence of metallo- β -lactamase-producing *P.putida* is an important clinical problem, representing a reservoir of genetic determinants of multi-drug resistance. The *P. putida* isolate PCR product which has been amplified and used as template for sequence reaction (Fig.1). The result of sequence alignment of *bla_{VIM}* sequence from Sulaimani hospitals against *bla_{VIM2}* gene of *.putida* class 1 integron which published by Lee *et al.* in 2002, in korea, (ACCESSION: AF327064.1) showed that the sequence has a length of about 3057 bp., identities were 792/803 (98%), which indicate that there were 11 mutations in *bla_{VIM}* of *p. putida* isolated from Sulaimani (Fig. 2).

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ATGTTCAAACCTTTTGAGTAAGTTATTGGTCTATTGACCGC
GTCTATCATGGCTATTGCGAGTCCGCTCGCTTTTCCGCTAG
ATTCTAGCGGTGAGTATCCGACAGTCAGCGAAATCCGGTC
GGGAGGTCGGGCTTTACCAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGGTTC
GCATATCGCAACCGCGGTCTGATGGCGCAGCTACCCCGT
CCAATGGTCTCATTGTCCGTGATGGTATGAGTTGCTTTGA
TTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGGCAAAAACACAGCGGCACTTCT
CGCGGAGATTGAGAAGCAAATTGGACTTCTGTAACGCGT
GCAGTCTCCACGCACTTTCATGACGACCGCGTCGGCGGCGT
TGATGTCTTCGGGCGGCTGGGGTGGCAGGTCACGCATCACC
CTCGACACGCGGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGGAGATT
GCCACGCACTCTCTAGAAGGACTTCTATCGACGCGGCTAGC
CAGTGCCTTCGGTCCAGTAGAACTTCTATCCTGGTGCT
GCGCATTGACCGACAACCTTAGTTGTGTACGTCCCGTCTGC
GAGTGTGCTCTATGGTGGTTGTGCGATTTATGAGTTGT
CACGCACGTC
TGCGGGGAACGTGGCCGATGCCGATCTGGCTGAATGGCCC
ACCTCCCATTGAGCGGATTCAACAACACTACCCGGAAGCA
CAGTTCGTCTATCCGGGGCACGGCTTCCGGGGCGGTCTAGA
CTTGCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGTA AAAAGCGCACACA
ACGCTCAGTCGTTGAGTAGCAGGCAGATGCGGCATAACAT
GAAGTT
    
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Fig. 1: Complete sequence of the *bla_{VIM}* gene in *P. putida* isolate

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Query 1 ATGTTCAAACCTTTTGAGTAAGTTATTGGTCTATTGACCGCTCTATCATGGCTATTGGC
Sbjct55 ATGTTCAAACCTTTTGAGTAAGTTATTGGTCTATTGACCGCTCTATCATGGCTATTGGC
Query 61 AGTCGCTCGCTTTTCCGCTAGATTCTAGCGGTGAGTATCCGACAGTCAGCGAAATCCCG
Sbjct613 AGTCGCTCGCTTTTCCGCTAGATTCTAGCGGTGAGTATCCGACAGTCAGCGAAATCCCG
Query121 GTCGGGGAGGTCGGGCTTTACCAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGGTTCGATATCGCAACGCGG
Sbjct673 GTCGGGGAGGTCGGGCTTTACCAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGGTTCGATATCGCAACGCGG
    
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Query 181 TCGTTTGATGGCGCAGTCTACCCGTCCTAATGGTCTCATTGTCCTGATGGTGATGAGTTG
Sbjct 733 TCGTTTGATGGCGCAGTCTACCCGTCCTAATGGTCTCATTGTCCTGATGGTGATGAGTTG
Query 241 CTTTTGATTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGCAGAAAACACAGCGGCACCTTCTCGCGGAGATTGAG
Sbjct 793 CTTTTGATTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGCAGAAAACACAGCGGCACCTTCTCGCGGAGATTGAG
Query 301 AAGCAAATGGACTTCCTGTAACGCGTGCAGTCTCCACGCACTTTCATGACGACCGGCTC
Sbjct 853 AAGCAAATGGACTTCCTGTAACGCGTGCAGTCTCCACGCACTTTCATGACGACCGGCTC
Query 361 GCGCGGTTGATGTCCTTCAGGCGGCTGGGGTGGCAACGTACGCATCACCGTCGACACGC
Sbjct 913 GCGCGGTTGATGTCCTTCAGGCGGCTGGGGTGGCAACGTACGCATCACCGTCGACACGC
Query 421 CGGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGAGATTCCACGCACTCTCTAGAAGGACTCTCATCG
Sbjct 973 CGGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGAGATTCCACGCACTCTCTAGAAGGACTCTCATCG
Query 481 AGCGGGGACGT-GCCACGCTTCGGTCCAGTAGAACTCT-CTTATCCTGGTCTCGCATT
Sbjct 1033AGCGGGGACGAGTG-CGCTTCGGTCCAGTAGAACTCTCT-ATCCTGGTCTCGCATT
Query 539 CGACCGACAACCTAGTTGTGTACGTCGCCCTCTGCGAGTGTGCTCTATGGTGGTTGTGCGA
Sbjct 1091CGACCGACAACCTAGTTGTGTACGTCGCCCTCTGCGAGTGTGCTCTATGGTGGTTGTGCGA
Query 599 TTTATGAGTTGTACGCAAGCTCTGCGGGGAGCGTGGCCGATCCGATCTGGCTGAATGGC
Sbjct 1151TTTATGAGTTGTACGCAAGCTCTGCGGGGAGCGTGGCCGATCCGATCTGGCTGAATGGC
Query 659 CCACCTCCATTGAGCGGATTCACAACTACTACCCGGAAGCACAGTTCGTCATTCCGGGGC
Sbjct 1211CCACCTCCATTGAGCGGATTCACAACTACTACCCGGAAGCACAGTTCGTCATTCCGGGGC
Query 719 ACGGCTCCCGGGCGGTCTAGACTTGTCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGTAAGGCGCAC
Sbjct 1271ACGGCTCCCGGGCGGTCTAGACTTGTCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGTAAGGCGCAC
Query 779 CAAATCGCTCAGTCGTTGAGTAG 801
Sbjct 1331CAAATCGCTCAGTCGTTGAGTAG 1353

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Fig. 2 Sequence alignment of *bla_{Vim}* sequence from Sulaimani hospitals against *Vim2* gene of *p. putida* class 1 integron (*bla_{VIM-2}*), (ACCESSION: AF327064.1)

Sequence alignment of *bla_{Vim}* sequence from Sulaimani hospitals against *Vim6* gene of *p. putida* strain DU25165/00 (*bla_{VIM-6}*) (ACCESSION: AY165025.1). Sequence has a length of about 828 bp. Identities were 821/830 (98%) (Fig 4). The results showed that there were 9 mutations for the *bla_{Vim 6}* of *p. putida* strain DU25165/00 which was first published by Koh *et al.*, in (2004)(5) in Singapore (Fig 3).

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Query 1 ATGTTCAAACCTTTGAGTAAGTTATTGGTCTATTTGACCGGCTCTATCATGGCTATTGCG
Sbjct 1 ATGTTCAAACCTTTGAGTAAGTTATTGGTCTATTTGACCGGCTCTATCATGGCTATTGCG
Query 61 AGTCCGCTCGCTTTTCCGTAAGTTCTAGCGGTGAGTATCCGACAGTCAGCGAAATTCGG
Sbjct 61 AGTCCGCTCGCTTTTCCGTAAGTTCTAGCGGTGAGTATCCGACAGTCAGCGAAATTCGG
Query 121 GTCGGGGAGGTCGGCTTTACCAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGGTGCATATCGCAACCGGG
Sbjct 121 GTCGGGGAGGTCGGCTTTACCAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGGTGCATATCGCAACCGGG
Query 181 TCGTTTGATGGCGCAGTCTACCCGTCCTAATGGTCTCATTGTCCTGATGGTGATGAGTTG
Sbjct 181 TCGTTTGATGGCGCAGTCTACCCGTCCTAATGGTCTCATTGTCCTGATGGTGATGAGTTG
Query 241 CTTTTGATTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGCAGAAAACACAGCGGCACCTTCTCGCGGAGATTGAG
Sbjct 241 CTTTTGATTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGCAGAAAACACAGCGGCACCTTCTCGCGGAGATTGAG
Query 301 AAGCAAATGGACTTCCTGTAACGCGTGCAGTCTCCACGCACTTTCATGACGACCGGCTC
Sbjct 301 AAGCAAATGGACTTCCTGTAACGCGTGCAGTCTCCACGCACTTTCATGACGACCGGCTC
Query 361 GCGCGGTTGATGTCCTTCAGGCGGCTGGGGTGGCAACGTACGCATCACCGTCGACACGC
Sbjct 361 GCGCGGTTGATGTCCTTCAGGCGGCTGGGGTGGCAACGTACGCATCACCGTCGACACGC
Query 421 CGGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGAGATTCCACGCACTCTCTAGAAGGACTCTCATCG
Sbjct 421 CGGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGAGATTCCACGCACTCTCTAGAAGGACTCTCATCG
Query 481 AGCGGGGACGT-GCCACGCTTCGGTCCAGTAGAACTCT-CTTATCCTGGTCTCGCATT
Sbjct 481 AGCGGGGACGAGTG-CGCTTCGGTCCAGTAGAACTCTCT-ATCCTGGTCTCGCATT
Query 539 CGACCGACAACCTAGTTGTGTACGTCGCCCTCTGCGAGTGTGCTCTATGGTGGTTGTGCGA
Sbjct 1993 CGACCGACAACCTAGTTGTGTACGTCGCCCTCTGCGAGTGTGCTCTATGGTGGTTGTGCGA
Query 599 TTTATGAGTTGTACGCAAGCTCTGCGGGGAGCGTGGCCGATCCGATCTGGCTGAATGGC
Sbjct 205 TTTATGAGTTGTACGCAAGCTCTGCGGGGAGCGTGGCCGATCCGATCTGGCTGAATGGC
Query 659 CCACCTCCATTGAGCGGATTCACAACTACTACCCGGAAGCACAGTTCGTCATTCCGGGGC
Sbjct 2113 CCACCTCCATTGAGCGGATTCACAACTACTACCCGGAAGCACAGTTCGTCATTCCGGGGC
Query 719 ACGGCTCCCGGGCGGTCTAGACTTGTCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGTAAGGCGCAC
Sbjct 2173 ACGGCTCCCGGGCGGTCTAGACTTGTCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGTAAGGCGCAC
Query 779 CAAATCGCTCAGTCGTTGAGTAG
Sbjct 2233 CAAATCGCTCAGTCGTTGAGTAG

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Query 659 CCACCTCCATTGAGCGGATTCACAACTACTACCCGGAAGCACAGTTCGTCATTCCGGGGC
Sbjct 659 CCACCTCCATTGAGCGGATTCACAACTACTACCCGGAAGCACAGTTCGTCATTCCGGGGC
Query 719 ACGGCTCCCGGGCGGTCTAGACTTGTCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGTAAGGCGCAC
Sbjct 719 ACGGCTCCCGGGCGGTCTAGACTTGTCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGTAAGGCGCAC
Query 779 CAAATCGCTCAGTCGTTGAGTAGCAGGCAGATCGGCATACATGAAGTT
Sbjct 779 CAAATCGCTCAGTCGTTGAGTAGCAGGCAGATCGGCATACATGAAGTT

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Fig. 3 Sequence alignment of *bla_{Vim}* sequence from Sulaimani hospital against *Vim6* gene of *p. putida* strain DU25165/00 (*bla_{VIM-6}*) (ACCESSION : AY165025.1)

Sequence alignment of *bla_{Vim}* sequence from Sulaimani hospitals against *Vim2* gene of *p. putida* strain YMC 98/2/665 class I integron (*bla_{VIM-2}*), (ACCESSION: AY907717.1). Sequence has a length of about 5325 bp. Identities were 792/803 (98%). The results showed that there were 11 mutations for the *bla_{Vim 2}* of *p. putida* strain YMC 98/2/665 which was first identified in Korea in 2005 by Yan (19) (Fig. 4).

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Query 1 ATGTTCAAACCTTTGAGTAAGTTATTGGTCTATTTGACCGGCTCTATCATGGCTATTGCG
Sbjct 1455 ATGTTCAAACCTTTGAGTAAGTTATTGGTCTATTTGACCGGCTCTATCATGGCTATTGCG
Query 61 AGTCCGCTCGCTTTTCCGTAAGTTCTAGCGGTGAGTATCCGACAGTCAGCGAAATTCGG
Sbjct 1515 AGTCCGCTCGCTTTTCCGTAAGTTCTAGCGGTGAGTATCCGACAGTCAGCGAAATTCGG
Query 121 GTCGGGGAGGTCGGCTTTACCAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGGTGCATATCGCAACCGGG
Sbjct 1575 GTCGGGGAGGTCGGCTTTACCAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGGTGCATATCGCAACCGGG
Query 181 TCGTTTGATGGCGCAGTCTACCCGTCCTAATGGTCTCATTGTCCTGATGGTGATGAGTTG
Sbjct 1635 TCGTTTGATGGCGCAGTCTACCCGTCCTAATGGTCTCATTGTCCTGATGGTGATGAGTTG
Query 241 CTTTTGATTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGCAGAAAACACAGCGGCACCTTCTCGCGGAGATTGAG
Sbjct 1695 CTTTTGATTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGCAGAAAACACAGCGGCACCTTCTCGCGGAGATTGAG
Query 301 AAGCAAATGGACTTCCTGTAACGCGTGCAGTCTCCACGCACTTTCATGACGACCGGCTC
Sbjct 1755 AAGCAAATGGACTTCCTGTAACGCGTGCAGTCTCCACGCACTTTCATGACGACCGGCTC
Query 361 GCGCGGTTGATGTCCTTCAGGCGGCTGGGGTGGCAACGTACGCATCACCGTCGACACGC
Sbjct 1815 GCGCGGTTGATGTCCTTCAGGCGGCTGGGGTGGCAACGTACGCATCACCGTCGACACGC
Query 421 CGGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGAGATTCCACGCACTCTCTAGAAGGACTCTCATCG
Sbjct 1875 CGGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGAGATTCCACGCACTCTCTAGAAGGACTCTCATCG
Query 481 AGCGGGGACGT-GCCACGCTTCGGTCCAGTAGAACTCT-CTTATCCTGGTCTCGCATT
Sbjct 1935 AGCGGGGACGAGTG-CGCTTCGGTCCAGTAGAACTCTCT-ATCCTGGTCTCGCATT
Query 539 CGACCGACAACCTAGTTGTGTACGTCGCCCTCTGCGAGTGTGCTCTATGGTGGTTGTGCGA
Sbjct 1993 CGACCGACAACCTAGTTGTGTACGTCGCCCTCTGCGAGTGTGCTCTATGGTGGTTGTGCGA
Query 599 TTTATGAGTTGTACGCAAGCTCTGCGGGGAGCGTGGCCGATCCGATCTGGCTGAATGGC
Sbjct 205 TTTATGAGTTGTACGCAAGCTCTGCGGGGAGCGTGGCCGATCCGATCTGGCTGAATGGC
Query 659 CCACCTCCATTGAGCGGATTCACAACTACTACCCGGAAGCACAGTTCGTCATTCCGGGGC
Sbjct 2113 CCACCTCCATTGAGCGGATTCACAACTACTACCCGGAAGCACAGTTCGTCATTCCGGGGC
Query 719 ACGGCTCCCGGGCGGTCTAGACTTGTCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGTAAGGCGCAC
Sbjct 2173 ACGGCTCCCGGGCGGTCTAGACTTGTCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGTAAGGCGCAC
Query 779 CAAATCGCTCAGTCGTTGAGTAG
Sbjct 2233 CAAATCGCTCAGTCGTTGAGTAG

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Fig. 4 Sequence alignment of *bla_{Vim}* sequence from Sulaimani hospitals against *Vim2* gene of *p. putida* strain YMC 98/2/665 class I integron (*bla_{VIM-2}*), (ACCESSION: AY907717.1)

Sequence alignment of *bla_{Vim}* sequence from Sulaimani hospitals against *Vim2* gene of *p. putida* transposon Tn1332 (ACCESSION: DQ174113.1). The sequence has a length of about 11132 bp. Identities were 792/803 (98%) (Fig. 5). The results showed that there were 11 mutations for the *bla_{Vim}* of *p.*

putida transposon Tn1332 which was first published in 2006 by Poirel *et al.*, in France[11].

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Query 1 ATGTTCAAACCTTTTGAAGTAAGTTATTGGTCTATTGACCGCGTCTATCATGGCTATTGG
Sbjct 5718 ATGTTCAAACCTTTTGAAGTAAGTTATTGGTCTATTGACCGCGTCTATCATGGCTATTGG

Query 61 AGTCCGCTCGCTTTTTCCGTAGATTCTAGCGGTGAGTATCCGACAGTCAGCGAAATTCGG
Sbjct 5778 AGTCCGCTCGCTTTTTCCGTAGATTCTAGCGGTGAGTATCCGACAGTCAGCGAAATTCGG

Query 121 GTCGGGAGGTCCGGCTTTACCAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGTTGTCGCATATCGCAACCGCG
Sbjct 5838 GTCGGGAGGTCCGGCTTTACCAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGTTGTCGCATATCGCAACCGCG

Query 181 TCGTTTGATGGCGCAGTCTACCCGTCGAATGGTCTCATTGTCCTGATGGTATGAGTTG
Sbjct 5898 TCGTTTGATGGCGCAGTCTACCCGTCGAATGGTCTCATTGTCCTGATGGTATGAGTTG

Query 241 CTTTTGATTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGCAGAAAAACACAGCGCACTTCTCGCGGAGATTGAG
Sbjct 5958 CTTTTGATTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGCAGAAAAACACAGCGCACTTCTCGCGGAGATTGAG

Query 301 AAGCAAATGGACTTCCTGTAACCGGTGAGTCTCCACGCATTTTCATGACGACCGCGTC
Sbjct 6018 AAGCAAATGGACTTCCTGTAACCGGTGAGTCTCCACGCATTTTCATGACGACCGCGTC

Query 361 GCGCGCTTGATGTCCTTCAGCGCGTGGGGTGGCAACGTACGCATCACCGTCGACACCG
Sbjct 6078 GCGCGCTTGATGTCCTTCAGCGCGTGGGGTGGCAACGTACGCATCACCGTCGACACCG

Query 421 CGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGAGATTCCACGCACCTCTCTAGAAGGACTCTCATCG
Sbjct 6138 CGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGAGATTCCACGCACCTCTCTAGAAGGACTCTCATCG

Query 481 AGCGGGACGCT-GCCACGCTTCGGTCCAGTAGAAGTCT-CTTATCCTGGTCTCGCGATT
Sbjct 6198 AGCGGGACGCT-GCCACGCTTCGGTCCAGTAGAAGTCT-CTTATCCTGGTCTCGCGATT

Query 539 CGACCGACAACCTAGTTGTGTACGTCCTCCGTCCTCCGAGTGTGCTCTATGGTGGTGTGCGA
Sbjct 6256 CGACCGACAACCTAGTTGTGTGTACGTCCTCCGTCCTCCGAGTGTGCTCTATGGTGGTGTGCGA

Query 599 TTTATGAGTTGTACGACAGTCTCGCGGGAGCGTGGCCGATGCCGATCTGGCTGAATGCG
Sbjct 6316 TTTATGAGTTGTACGACAGTCTCGCGGGAGCGTGGCCGATGCCGATCTGGCTGAATGCG

Query 659 CCACCTCCATTGAGCGGATTCAACAACACTACCCGGAAGCACAGTTCGTCATTCCGGGGC
Sbjct 6376 CCACCTCCATTGAGCGGATTCAACAACACTACCCGGAAGCACAGTTCGTCATTCCGGGGC

Query 719 ACGGCTGCCGGCGGTCTAGACTTGCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGAAAAGCGCAC
Sbjct 6436 ACGGCTGCCGGCGGTCTAGACTTGCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGAAAAGCGCAC

Query 779 CAAATCGCTCAGTCGTTGAGTAG
Sbjct 6496 CAAATCGCTCAGTCGTTGAGTAG
    
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Fig. 5 Sequence alignment of *bla_{Vim}* sequence from Sulaimani hospitals against *Vim2* gene of *p. putida* transposon Tn1332 (ACCESSION : DQ174113.1)

Sequence alignment of *bla_{Vim}* sequence from Sulaimani hospitals against *Vim1* gene of *p. putida* strain A2580/277 (VIM-1) gene, (ACCESSION : EU118150.1). The sequence has a length of about 843 bp, Identities were 738/809 (91%) (Fig. 6). The results showed that there were 71 mutations for the *bla_{Vim1}* of *p. putida* strain A2580/277 which was first identified in Greece by Papadopoulou *et al.* in 2007[12].

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Query 1 ATGTTCAAACCTTTTGAAGTAAGTTATTGGTCTATTGACCGCGTCTATCATGGCTATTGG
Sbjct 40 ATGTTAAAAGTTATT-AGT-AGTTTATTGGTCTACATGACCGCGTCTGTATGGCTGTGCG

Query 59 CGAGTCCGCTCGCTTTTTCCGTAGATTCTAGCGGTGAGTATCCGACAGTCAGCGAAATTC
Sbjct 98 CAAGTCCGTTAGCCCAATTCGCGGGAGCGGATGGTGTGATATCCGACAGTCAACGAAATTC

Query 119 CGTCCGGGAGGTCCGGCTTTACCAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGTTGTCGCATATCGCAACCG
Sbjct 158 CGTCCGGGAGGTCCGGCTTTACCAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGTTGTCGCATATCGCAACCG

Query 179 GGTCTGTTGATGGCGCAGTCTACCCGTCGAATGGTCTCATTGTCCTGATGGTATGAGT
Sbjct 218 AGTCTGTTGATGGCGCGTCTACCCGTCGAATGGTCTCATTGTCCTGATGGTATGAGT

Query 239 TGCTTTTGAATTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGCAGAAAAACACAGCGCACTTCTCGCGGAGATTG
Sbjct 278 TGCTTTTGAATTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGCAGAAAAACACAGCGCACTTCTCGCGGAGATTG

Query 299 AGAAGCAAATGGACTTCCTGTAACCGGTGAGTCTCCACGCATTTTCATGACGACCGCG
Sbjct 338 AAGCAAATGGACTTCCTGTAACCGGTGAGTCTCCACGCATTTTCATGACGACCGCG

Query 359 TCGGCGCGTTGATGTCCTTCAGCGCGTGGGGTGGCAACGTACGCATCACCGTCGACAC
Sbjct 398 TCGGCGCGTTGATGTCCTTCAGCGCGTGGGGTGGCAACGTACGCATCACCGTCGACAC
    
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Query 419 GCCGGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGAGATTCCACGCACCTCTCTAGAAGGACTCTCAT
Sbjct 458 GCCGGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGAGATTCCACGCACCTCTCTAGAAGGACTCTCAT

Query 479 CGAGCGGGGACGT-GCCACGCTTCGGTCCAGTAGAAGTCT-CTTATCCTGGTGTGTCGCGA
Sbjct 518 CGAGCGGGGACGT-GCCACGCTTCGGTCCAGTAGAAGTCT-CTTATCCTGGTGTGTCGCGA

Query 537 TTCGACCCGACAA-CTTAGTTGTGTACGTCCTCGCTGCGAGTGTGCTCTATGTTGGTGTG
Sbjct 576 TTCGACCCGACAACTG-GTTGTATAGTCCCGTCAGCGAACGTGCTATACCGTGGTGTG

Query 596 C-GATTTATGAGTTGTACGACGCTCTCGGGGAGCGTGGCCGATGCCGATCTGGCTGAA
Sbjct 635 CCG-TTCATGAGTTGTCAAGCAGCTCTCGGGGAGCGTGGCCGATGCCGATCTGGCTGAA

Query 655 TGGCCACCTCCATTGAGCGGATTCAACAACACTACCCGGAAGCACAGTTCGTCATTCCG
Sbjct 694 TGGCCACCTCCGTTGAGCGGATTCAAAAACACTACCCGGAAGCACAGTTCGTCATTCCG

Query 715 GGGCACGGCTGCGGGCGGTCTAGACTTCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGAAAAGCG
Sbjct 754 GGGCACGGCTTACGCGGCTTAGACTTCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGAAAAGCG

Query 775 CACACAATCGCTCAGTCGTTGAGTAGCA
Sbjct 814 CACAAAATCGCTCAGTCGCGGAGTAGCA
    
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Fig. 6 Sequence alignment of *bla_{Vim}* sequence from Sulaimani hospitals against *Vim1* gene of *p. putida* strain A2580/277 (VIM-1) gene, (ACCESSION : EU118150.1)

Sequence alignment of *bla_{Vim}* DNA sequence from Sulaimani hospitals against *Vim* gene of *p. putida* strain PFi class 1 integron (ACCESSION FJ237530). The sequence has a length of about 1904 bp. Identities between the *bla_{Vim}* DNA sequence from Sulaimani hospitals and *bla_{Vim2}* of *p. putida* strain PFi isolated in Portugal were 792/803 (98%) (Fig. 7). The results showed there were 10 mutations for the *bla_{Vim2}* of *p. putida* strain PFi which include transversion, deletion and insertion).The information about this sequence was first submitted by Santos *et al.*(2008) in Portugal [16].

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Query ATGTTCAAACCTTTTGAAGTAAGTTATTGGTCTATTGACCGCGTCTATCATGGCTATTGG
Sbjct ATGTTCAAACCTTTTGAAGTAAGTTATTGGTCTATTGACCGCGTCTATCATGGCTATTGG

Query AGTCCGCTCGCTTTTTCCGTAGATTCTAGCGGTGAGTATCCGACAGTCAGCGAAATTCGG
Sbjct AGTCCGCTCGCTTTTTCCGTAGATTCTAGCGGTGAGTATCCGACAGTCAGCGAAATTCGG

Query GTCGGGAGGTCCGGCTTTACCAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGTTGTCGCATATCGCAACCGCG
Sbjct GTCGGGAGGTCCGGCTTTACCAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGTTGTCGCATATCGCAACCGCG

Query TCGTTTGATGGCGCAGTCTACCCGTCGAATGGTCTCATTGTCCTGATGGTATGAGTTG
Sbjct TCGTTTGATGGCGCAGTCTACCCGTCGAATGGTCTCATTGTCCTGATGGTATGAGTTG

Query CTTTTGATTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGCAGAAAAACACAGCGCACTTCTCGCGGAGATTGAG
Sbjct CTTTTGATTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGCAGAAAAACACAGCGCACTTCTCGCGGAGATTGAG

Query AAGCAAATGGACTTCCTGTAACCGGTGAGTCTCCACGCATTTTCATGACGACCGCGTC
Sbjct AAGCAAATGGACTTCCTGTAACCGGTGAGTCTCCACGCATTTTCATGACGACCGCGTC

Query GCGCGCTTGATGTCCTTCAGCGCGTGGGGTGGCAACGTACGCATCACCGTCGACACCG
Sbjct GCGCGCTTGATGTCCTTCAGCGCGTGGGGTGGCAACGTACGCATCACCGTCGACACCG

Query CGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGAGATTCCACGCACCTCTCTAGAAGGACTCTCATCG
Sbjct CGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGAGATTCCACGCACCTCTCTAGAAGGACTCTCATCG

Query AGCGGGACGCT-GCCACGCTTCGGTCCAGTAGAAGTCT-CTTATCCTGGTCTCGCGATT
Sbjct AGCGGGACGCT-GCCACGCTTCGGTCCAGTAGAAGTCT-CTTATCCTGGTCTCGCGATT

Query CGACCGACAACCTAGTTGTGTACGTCCTCCGTCCTCCGAGTGTGCTCTATGGTGGTGTGCGA
Sbjct CGACCGACAACCTAGTTGTGTGTACGTCCTCCGTCCTCCGAGTGTGCTCTATGGTGGTGTGCGA

Query TTTATGAGTTGTACGACAGTCTCGCGGGAGCGTGGCCGATGCCGATCTGGCTGAATGCG
Sbjct TTTATGAGTTGTACGACAGTCTCGCGGGAGCGTGGCCGATGCCGATCTGGCTGAATGCG

Query CCACCTCCATTGAGCGGATTCAACAACACTACCCGGAAGCACAGTTCGTCATTCCGGGGC
Sbjct CCACCTCCATTGAGCGGATTCAACAACACTACCCGGAAGCACAGTTCGTCATTCCGGGGC

Query ACGGCTGCCGGCGGTCTAGACTTGCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGAAAAGCGCAC
Sbjct ACGGCTGCCGGCGGTCTAGACTTGCTCAAGCACACAACGAATGTTGAAAAGCGCAC

Query CAAATCGCTCAGTCGTTGAGTAG
Sbjct CAAATCGCTCAGTCGTTGAGTAG
    
```

Fig. 7 Sequence alignment of Sequence alignment of *bla_{Vim}* DNA sequence from Sulaimani hospitals against *Vim* gene of *p. putida* strain PFI class I integron (ACCESSION FJ237530)

Sequence alignment of *bla_{Vim}* sequence from Sulaimani hospitals against *Vim4* gene of *p. putida* strain 283-02 class I integron (ACCESSION : FM179466.1). The sequence has a length of about 3329 bp. Identities between the *bla_{Vim}* sequence from Sulaimani hospitals and *bla_{Vim4}* of *p. putida* strain 283-02 isolated in Poland were 736/807 (91%) (Fig. 8). The results showed that there were 71 mutations for the *bla_{Vim}* 2 of *p. putida* strain 283-02 which was first published in 2009 by Patzar *et al.*, in Poland [9].

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Query 1   ATGTTCAAACCTT-TTGAGTAAG-TTATTTGGTCTATTTGACCGCGTCTATCATGGCTATTG
Sbjct 274 ATGTTAAAAGTTAATT-AGT-AGTTTATTTGGTCTACATGACCGCGTCTGTATGGCTGTGCG

Query 59  CGAGTCCGCTCGCTTTTCCGATAGATTCTAGCGGTGAGTATCCGACAGTCAGCGAAATTC
Sbjct 332 CAAGTCGTTAGCCCAATTCGCGGAGCCGAGTGGTGGTATCCGACAGTCAACGAAATTC

Query 119 CGGTCGGGGAGGTCGGCTTTTACAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGTTGGTCCGATATCGCAACGC
Sbjct 392 CGGTCGGAGAGGTCGCACTTTACAGATTGCCGATGGTGTGTTGGTCCGATATCGCAACGC

Query 179 GGTCTGTTGATGGCGCAGTCTACCCGTCCTAATGGTCTCATTGTCCTGATGGTGTGATGAT
Sbjct 452 AGTCTGTTGATGGCGCGTCTACCCGTCCTAATGGTCTCATTGTCCTGATGGTGTGATGATGAT

Query 239 TGCTTTTGTATTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGGCAAAAACACAGCGGCACTTCTCGCGAGATTG
Sbjct 512 TGCTTTTGTATTGATACAGCGTGGGGTGGCAAAAACACAGCGGCACTTCTCGCGAGATTG

Query 299 AGAAGCAAATTTGACTTCTCTGTAACCGGTGCACTCTCCACGCACTTTTATGACGACCGG
Sbjct 572 AAAAGCAAATTTGACTTCTCCGTAACCGGTGCACTCTCCACGCACTTTTATGACGACCGG

Query 359 TCGGCGCGTGTGATGCTCTTACGCGGCTGGGGTGGCAACGTACGCACTCAGCGACAC
Sbjct 632 TCGGCGCGTGTGATGCTCTTACGCGGCTGGGGTGGCAACGTACGCACTCAGCGACAC

Query 419 GCCGGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGAGATTCCACGCACTCTCTAGAAGGACTCTCAT
Sbjct 692 GCCGGCTAGCCGAGGTAGAGGGGAGCGAGATTCCACGCACTCTCTAGAAGGACTCTCAT

Query 479 CGAGCGGGGACGT-GCCACGCTTCGGTCCAGTAGAAGTCT-CTTATCTGGTCTGCGCA
Sbjct 752 CGAGCGGGGACGCAAGT-GCCTTCGTTCCAGTAGAGTCTTCT-ATCTGGTCTGCGCA

Query 537 TTCGACCGACAA-CTTAGTTGTGTACGCTCCCGCTCGGAGTGTGCTCTATGGTGGTTGTG
Sbjct 810 TTCGACCGACAACTG-GTTGTATACGCTCCCGCTCAGCGAAGTGTCTATACGGTGGTTGTG

Query 596 C-GATTTATGAGTTGTGACCGCAGCTCTCGGGGAGCGTGGCCGATCCGCGATCTGGCTGAA
Sbjct 869 CCG-TTCATGAGTTGTGACCGCAGCTCTCGGGGAGCGTGGCCGATCCGCGATCTGGCTGAA

Query 655 TGGCCCACTCCATTGAGCGGATTCAACAACTACCCGGAAGCAGAGTTCGTCATTCCG
Sbjct 928 TGGCCCACTCCCGTTGAGCGGATTCAAAAACTACCCGGAAGCAGAGTTCGTCATTCCG

Query 715 GGGCACGGCTGCGCGGCGTCTAGACTTGTCTCAAGCACACACGAATGTTGTAAGAGCG
Sbjct 988 GGGCACGGTCTACCGGCGGCTAGACTTGTCTCCAGCACACAGGAAAGTTCGTAAGAGCA

Query 775 CACACAAATCGCTCAGTCTGATGATG
Sbjct 1048 CACAAAAATCGCTCAGTCTGCGGAGTAG

```

Fig. 8 Sequence alignment of *bla_{Vim}* sequence from Sulaimani hospitals against *Vim4* gene of *p. putida* strain 283-02 class I integron (ACCESSION : FM179466.1)

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2- Emergency of vancomycin resistant Staphylococcus aureus burned patients in Emergency hospital in Sulaimani city, Kurdistan region, Iraq. Journal of Karkok University.

3- Comparison of Tn1546 element of vancomycin resistant Staphylococcus aureus isolated from burned patients in Sulaimani hospital. Published in International conference proceeding on bioinformatics and biomedical technology -April 2010.

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5- Participated in “International Conference on Biological Science and Engineering” in 24-26 Nov. 2010 , Venice, Italy.